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**CORRELATIONS BETWEEN PERCEIVED PARENTING STYLES AND THE
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF COLLEGE STUDENTS**

Social Work

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Abstract:

Parenting plays a crucial part in providing learning environment to children. It has become a difficult task for every parent. Emotional Intelligence is the need of the hour for any youth to succeed in their personal and professional life. This paper presents the findings related to the perceived parenting styles, status of Emotional Intelligence and the correlations between the parenting styles and the Emotional Intelligence. Descriptive design was used, questionnaire method was used to collect data from 520 college students. This paper reveals that majority of the students have perceived their parents with Non-Ideal (Permissive and Authoritarian) style of parenting. Majority of the students lack Emotional Intelligence and there are positive correlations between the different facets of Emotional Intelligence and parenting styles. This paper calls for efforts by parents and educational institutions to facilitate ideal parenting among the parents, which would yield higher Emotional Intelligence among the youth.

Key Words: *Parenting Styles and Emotional Intelligence*

Introduction

Human body is actually the product of parents, but the behaviour and intelligence is to larger extent the product of environment in which a child grows. Most people would agree that parenting is not an easy job. In fact, it is one of the hardest tasks, as every parent would hope to succeed in parenting. Parenting style is one of the variables that have been studied extensively in human development (Cowan and Cowan: 1998). Parenting is considered to be an important determinant of several aspects of children's outcome (Volpe: 2010). As recent world events have taught, there is a danger to each of us-locally and globally-when children grow up with knowledge but without social-emotional skills and a strong moral compass. Hence, emotional learning is the true standard for effective education in the world today and for the foreseeable future and parents have greater responsibility to sense the necessity of adopting authoritative parenting styles.

.Parenting Styles

Parenting plays a major role in the emotional aspects of children and imitation takes place consciously or unconsciously as they grow. Parenting styles have been described as the collection of parents' behaviours, which create an atmosphere of parent-child interactions across situations (Mize & Pettit, 1997). Based on the work of Baumrind (e.g., 1967; 1978; 1995) and those who have extended her work (e.g., Maccoby, 1983 & Roberts, 1986), several broad typologies of parenting styles (i.e., authoritative, authoritarian and permissive) have been identified. Taken together, the styles of authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting differ in several important features including (a) support shown to a child aimed at forming an emotional connection with the child, (b) behavioural control of the child aimed at promoting mature behaviour, and (c) autonomy granting aimed at fostering self-reliance (Hart, 2003).

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence has been the key area of wide attention since it was popularized by Goleman in 1995. In an historical context, emotion and cognition have both been recognized

as distinct entities with varying levels of importance depending on historical and cultural perceptions. According to Salovey and Mayer (1990), emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to be aware and manage oneself and other people from the aspect of feeling and emotion, able to distinguish the two terms apart and able to use the information to guide one's thinking and act. Emotional intelligence also enables an individual to control self-impetus. Furthermore, according to Goleman, the level of Intelligence contributes only about 20% towards one's accomplishment, while the rest are determined by emotional intelligence. (Goleman, 1998). Trait emotional intelligence (trait EI or trait emotional self-efficacy) is defined as a constellation of emotion-related self-perceptions and dispositions located at the lower levels of personality hierarchies (Petrides, 2006).

Significance of the Study

Emotional Intelligence is very much emphasized in almost all the industrial sectors. At the same time, Emotional Intelligence is still a new field of research for most of the educational institutions. Though there is an increase in the number of regular and distance education systems in India, it has been criticized as the agents producing qualified unemployable candidates. There is a great insist for excellent job skills and emotional intelligence to work with and handle human resources. Parents have greater responsibility for shaping the children emotionally intelligent and academically excellent. The effort of any country in making young a smart and productive is possible only through the way parents and educational institutions up bring by imparting necessary skills and knowledge. Emotional intelligence is imperative to cope up with the emerging worldly challenges and pressures and to be a successful person at work and relations. Hence, this paper highlights the perceived role of the parenting styles on the emotional intelligence of college students.

Specific Objectives

1. To find out the status of college students' emotional intelligence
2. To examine the parenting styles perceived by college students.

3. To identify the relationship between emotional intelligence and perceived parenting styles

Methodology

The study was carried out in the year 2012 at Sacred Heart College, which is a pioneering college that has educated thousands of rural youth since 1951. There are 13 UG departments, which functions in two shifts with 16 departments. There were 3558 students of both boys and girls for under graduations and post graduations. This college was graded as 'A' by NAAC (National Accreditation and assessment council) in 2004. The research adopted Descriptive Design under the educational and psychological model. Stratified disproportionate random sampling method was to derive 520 as sample size for the study. Petrides's (2001) Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire – Short Form (TEIQue-SF) consists of 30 items designed to measure global trait emotional intelligence was used to measure the Emotional Intelligence of the college students. The standardized tool on Parenting Authoritative Questionnaire developed by Baumrind (1971) was used to assess the perceived parenting styles by the students with 30 questions indicating the permissive, authoritarian and authoritative parenting styles of parenting. SPSS version 14.0 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) was used to process and analysis the data.

Analysis and Interpretations: The following table reveals the role of perceived parenting styles on the Emotional Intelligence of the College Students.

Status of Emotional Intelligence among College Students

Emotional intelligence is considered as an essential element in human dynamics. According to Petrides et, al (2007) the Emotional Intelligence is composed of fifteen facets; adaptability, assertiveness, emotion appraisal (self and others), emotion expression, emotion management (others), emotion regulation, impulsiveness (low), relationship skills, self-esteem, self-motivation, social competence, stress management, trait empathy, trait happiness, and trait optimism. These fifteen facets have been further classified into five factors namely wellbeing, emotionality, self-control, sociability and adaptability & self-motivation. The computed score for the emotional intelligence was classified as following by using Mean and Standard Deviation. The diagram depicts that majority (64.8%) of the respondents have moderate level of Emotional Intelligence. Nearly one fifth (18.8%) of them has higher Emotional Intelligence. To be precise, except the 18.8 percent of the students, majority of them were having moderate and lower level of emotional intelligence.

Perceived Parenting Styles

Majority (73.8%) of the respondents have perceived authoritative style of parenting from their parents. Hence, majority of the students perceived their parents as authoritative parents. This finding is in parallel with a study conducted by Elias and Tanhuey (2009) with 247 secondary school students that majority of his study respondents expressed that their parents were authoritative parents.

Ideal Parenting Style

he parenting styles were further classified into ideal and non-ideal parenting styles. The ideal parenting is a combination of parenting style by different levels (*lower permissive style, lower authoritarian style and higher authoritative style*), which has been as mostly highlighted

by Baumrind (1967; 1989; 1991). The ideal parenting makes the best atmosphere of parent-child interaction that impacts children’s cognitive and social development. The diagram reveals that only about 4.2 percent of the youth experienced ideal type of parenting from their parents and the rest about 95.8 percent have experienced non-ideal style of parenting.

Correlations between the Perceived Parenting Styles and Emotional Intelligence

		Permissive	Authoritarian	Authoritative
Wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.022	-.066	.359**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.612	.133	.000
	N	520	520	520
Self-Control	Pearson Correlation	.006	-.179**	.130**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.890	.000	.003
	N	520	520	520
Emotionality	Pearson Correlation	-.154**	-.183**	.227**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	520	520	520
Sociability	Pearson Correlation	-.075	-.301**	.121**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.088	.000	.006
	N	520	520	520
Global EI	Pearson Correlation	-.019	-.068	.249**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.657	.123	.000
	N	520	520	520
Emotional	Pearson Correlation	-.074	-.229**	.307**

Intelligence	Sig. (2-tailed)	.093	.000	.000
	N	520	520	520

Authoritative parenting style significantly contributes ($P < .05$) for all the emotional intelligence factors (wellbeing, emotionality, self-control, sociability and adaptability & self-motivation). Whereas, permissive and authoritarian style of parenting styles does not or negatively contribute ($P > .05$) for the development of Emotional Intelligence of students.

Role of Ideal Parenting on the Emotional Intelligence - Independent Samples Test

Group Statistics	Ideal and Non Ideal Parenting	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-test for Equality of Means		
					T	df	Sig.
Emotional Intelligence	Ideal Parenting	22	99.4091	6.38942	7.185	518	.000
	Weak Parenting	498	83.4157	10.34758			

The mean value of emotional intelligence of the students has significant difference ($P < .05$) according to the ideal and non-ideal parenting styles. The mean value of emotional intelligence is larger in the ideal parenting style ($M=99.4$), than the mean value of emotional intelligence by the non-ideal parenting ($M=83.41$). Adoption of lower permissive, lower authoritarian and higher authoritative parenting style contributes for the higher emotional intelligence and academic achievement among the students.

Results and Discussion

This study findings manifests the status of the parenting experienced by the youth and their correlations with their current status of the emotional intelligence. It was found that very less number of parents had ideal parenting. There is a positive correlation found with the Emotional Intelligence by the Authoritative parenting or Ideal parenting style. Whereas, Emotional Intelligence is not positively correlated with the parents with Permissive,

Authoritarian or Non-Ideal Parenting styles. Hence, the following suggestions would help the parents and children to improve their parenting and emotional intelligence in future.

1. Emotional Intelligence is necessary curriculum for empowering youth and hence, the institutions can facilitate such programs on a regular basis.
2. Family is a primary social institution, which has a greater responsibility to provide learning environment for their children. When parents are in conflict and in the world of stress, certainly they would unconsciously play a destructive role. Hence, Counselling facilities could be created in every educational institution and family-counselling centres could talk to the parents about the importance of adapting authoritative and authoritarian for the construction of emotional intelligence of children.
 - Emotional intelligence has become an inevitable training aspect in every industry to make the human resource powerful and resourceful. It would be meaningful and essential to insert Emotional Intelligence as an allied subject in Schools and Colleges.
 - Most of the rural women are members of Self Help Groups. There could an essential training programmes on Art of Parenting the Modern Young.
 - Government allots huge fund for youth empowerment and to create entrepreneurship skills of youth of rural and urban. It is suggested to government to fund to enhance the emotional intelligence of youth, teachers, parents and adolescents.
 - Training Programmes would benefit parents to develop with positive parenting skills to carve child with high emotional intelligence and academic excellence.

Conclusion

The growing technology and stressful family life has emphasised for the important understanding about the significant parenting styles needed for the present generation to help them acquire higher emotional intelligence to succeed in their career and life. Youth is one of the

major concerns in Social Work profession, which aims at positive youth development to solve youth problems and transform them resources for nation development. The findings of the study have highlighted the need for adopting authoritative parenting style for assisting and shaping children with the higher emotional intelligence. The educational institutions, Self Help Groups, youth trainers, family and youth counsellors, social workers and other researchers would employ the findings and recommendations of this study to make constructive youth towards constructive social change and national building.

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